

LEAST MASTERED COMPETENCIES OF COOKERY: BASES FOR STRATEGIC INTERVENTION MATERIAL DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

Culinary art is among the profession that is able to provide a wide-range of career opportunities for individuals who has a passion for cooking (Nuri, 2019). Cookery is defined as the preparation of food that is ready for the consumption which includes employing professional work of artisans and chefs all over the world (Batayola, 2017). In cookery, there are competencies that are essential in preparing food and these competencies are divided into three standards that consist of the basic competencies, common competencies and core competencies. However, despite these competencies that can be developed through learning, some students who are trying to master cooking, have weaknesses that can be a hindrance in acquiring new skills and knowledge to improve one's work which are considered to be the least mastered competencies. Least mastered competencies are defined to be the abilities and competencies of students that have gains least attention in learning (de Jesus, 2019). Thus, this study intends to assess the least mastered competencies of cookery as a bases for a strategic intervention material development. Wherein this study utilized a standardized pre-test and post-test to assess the competencies of the students in cookery before and after utilizing the intervention material. Hence, findings of the study show that there is a significant difference between the performance of the respondents on the least mastered skills before and after using the intervention material and there is no significant difference between the perception of the respondents on the proposed material when they are grouped according to profile.

Keywords: Culinary art, Cookery, pre-test, post-test